

1 **PIK3C2A activation in luminal A breast cancer.**

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7 Current therapeutic targeting approaches in medical oncology that utilize PI3K inhibitors for the treatment
8 of breast cancer consider only mutational profile when administering idelalisib, specifically targeting only
9 patients whose tumors contain mutations in PI3K components. We demonstrate here that PIK3C2A was
10 among the top 0.5% most activated transcriptome-wide in humans with luminal A breast cancer. We
11 suggest overactivation of PI3K in luminal A breast cancer, conferred by induction of wild-type PIK3C2A
12 (instead of PI3K subunit mutation) might effectively be managed by pharmacologic antagonism of PI3K at
13 p110delta with idelalisib. Thus, the data support a clinical approach in medical oncology and in breast
14 oncology that views PI3K inhibition as a targeted method of inducing cellular senescence in the treatment
15 resistant tumor by targeting homeostasis associated with energy transfer in the cell, a senescence
16 pathway that operates apparently independent of proliferative capacity.
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